

TIME SERIES REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF MALARIA INFECTION AT PNG UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

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*The authors declare
that no funding was
received for this work.*

Received: 01-April-2025

Accepted: 25-May-2025

Published: 06-June-2026

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This article is published in the **MSI Journal of Medicine and Medical Research (MSIJMMR)**
ISSN 3049-1401 (Online)

The journal is managed and published by MSI Publishers.

Volume 3, Issue 2 (May-Aug), 2026

ABSTRACT: The Malaria remains a well-known public health challenge in Papua New Guinea (PNG), especially in low-altitude coastal cities, such as Lae, where the Papua New Guinea University of Technology (Unitech) is situated. Using time series regression analysis, this study models and predicts malaria infection rates at the University Health Services (UHS) ranging from 2018 to 2024. Monthly malaria case counts were sourced from health clinic registers and analysed with descriptive statistics and seasonal decomposition along with autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) modelling with meteorological covariates (ARIMAX). Data of the original series were analysed using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test; to detect non-stationarity and this was resolved via first-order differencing. The seasonal analysis indicated that malaria cases reached a consistent peak period in March-June, which is corresponding with the wet season in Morobe Province. SARIMA (1,1,1) (0,1,1)₁₂ with rainfall as an exogenous variable yielded a mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) of 8.3%, indicating the best prediction accuracy. We find a statistically significant positive association between monthly rainfall and malaria incidence ($p < 0.001$). These findings complement evidence-based planning for malaria

prevention and control interventions appropriate to the Unitech campus community. The work in this study adds to the expanding literature on epidemiological research using data in PNG and highlights the significance of campus health surveillance systems.

Keywords: *malaria; time series analysis; SARIMA; ARIMA; seasonality; regression*

1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Malaria, stemming from Plasmodium parasites and spread by Anopheles mosquitoes, continues to impose tremendous pressure on public health systems in developing countries. Globally, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that there were 249 million malaria cases and 608,000 deaths in 2022, primarily concentrated in sub-Saharan Africa (WHO, 2023). Papua New Guinea (PNG) carries a disproportionately high burden in the Western Pacific Region. In 2020, PNG accounted for around 80% of approximately 1.7 million malaria cases reported in the WHO Western Pacific Region with an incidence of 164 per 1,000 population (Cleary, Hetzel & Clements, 2022). PNG continues to have one of the highest levels of malaria prevalence outside sub-Saharan Africa; 94 per cent of the population (Cleary et al., 2022) is at risk. Lae, PNG's second largest city and principal industrial city, is situated in Morobe Province in PNG's northern coastal area. Lae is situated in the low altitude region and has a tropical monsoon climate with warm high temperatures, high humidity and heavy seasonal rainfall, which are favourable conditions for year-round Anopheles mosquito breeding and malaria transmission (Kobayashi et al., 2016). The PNG University of Technology (Unitech) is located on a 233-hectare campus in Lae, and its student load comprises around 4,000 people from across PNG, including highland provinces where endemic malaria is less frequent (PNG University of Technology, 2024). Because they are potentially immunologically naïve to the local Plasmodium falciparum and P. vivax strains found in coastal Lae, these students serve as a highly exposed population to malaria infection. Time-series knowledge of prevalence of malaria infection in the Unitech campus community is necessary to develop preventive measures, resource targeting, and to forecast case burdens in the future.

The use of time series regression, such as autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) (Box et al., 2015) and its seasonal extension (SARIMA), is a rigorous statistical scheme for establishing trends, seasonal cycles and meteorological drivers in infectious disease data (Box et al., 2015). To date, similar methods have been successfully applied to malaria forecasting in South Asia, Africa, and the Pacific, but few studies have done this at a localised campus level and none have been undertaken in the PNG context.

1.2 Problem Statement

Despite its well-documented burden of malaria in Lae and Morobe Province, there appears to be insufficient quantitative epidemiological examination of malaria infection patterns, even in the PNG University of Technology campus community. University Health Services (UHS) at Unitech serves as the first point of contact for most students, faculty, and their dependants and hosts hundreds of malaria consultations annually. However, these case records have not been systematically analysed using formal statistical or time series methodologies. No such analyses prevent health planners at Unitech from being able to project seasonal spikes, time chemoprophylaxis campaigns, or assess the impact of climatic variables (especially rainfall and temperature) on malaria rates at the campus level. This study seeks to fill this important gap by using time series regression models on monthly malaria case data collected at Unitech UHS to identify temporal patterns and create short-term forecasts that can help with evidence-based campus health care.

1.3 Research Aims and Objectives

To this end, the objectives of this study are to model and predict monthly malaria infection rates at PNG University of Technology through time series regression analysis of the period 2018 to 2024. Particularly, the research aims to:

- Analyse the temporal distribution and seasonal patterns of malaria cases experienced in Unitech University Health Services between 2018 and 2024.
- Test for stationarity and identify the appropriate order of differencing for the malaria case time series.

- Fit and analyse the best performing ARIMA/SARIMA model based on information criteria (AIC, BIC).
- Evaluate the correlation between malaria incidence and climatic factors (rainfall and temperature) through ARIMAX modelling.
- Develop a 12-month ahead forecast of malaria cases for 2025 and assess the forecast accuracy using RMSE, MAE, and MAPE.

1.4 Scope and Limitations

This research was confined to PNG University of Technology campus in Lae, Morobe Province. The study uses monthly malaria case data from the University Health Services clinic and publicly available weather data from the Lae weather station operated by the PNG National Weather Service. The study period includes January 2018 to December 2024, with 84 monthly observations enough to enable a robust estimation of the time series model. Several limitations are acknowledged. First, clinic attendance data will not reflect the real burden of malaria as certain students and staff can be treated at off-campus facilities such as ANGAU Memorial Hospital or private clinics in Lae. Second, all diagnosis of malaria at UHS is done using RDTs (rapid diagnostic tests) which provide only limited microscopy confirmation, so it may be assumed some diagnostic misclassification has occurred. Third, the study does not consider variations in the Unitech student population throughout the study period, which would potentially alter crude case rates. Fourth, the ARIMA modelling framework assumes linearity and is not necessarily representative of complex non-linear dynamics underlying malaria transmission. These constraints must be taken into account when interpreting these findings.

2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Global Burden of Malaria

Malaria is one of the most important vector-borne infectious diseases worldwide. Malaria, caused by five types of Plasmodium parasites (mostly *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax*), is transmitted through the bite of infected female *Anopheles* mosquitoes and disproportionately affects people living in tropical and subtropical countries without

adequate healthcare provision (WHO, 2023). A total of 249 million malaria cases occurred in 85 countries in 2022, a global case load that has returned to pre-pandemic levels following COVID-19-driven disruptions, according to the World Health Organization World Malaria Report 2023. The vast majority is about 94% of global malaria cases and deaths is in sub-Saharan Africa.

Despite a 37% drop in malaria incidence worldwide between 2000 and 2015 (Cleary et al., 2022), momentum is lacking in recent years. Although the Western Pacific Region constitutes a smaller proportion of disease burden globally, the region is highly impacted as PNG is responsible for >85% of the malaria burden in the region (Seid Ahmed et al., 2025; WHO, 2023). It has been estimated that the temperature regime suitable for malaria transmission includes an interval of 19.1°C through 30.1°C, which is exacerbated by rainfall, where a change of one millimetre per day in the level of precipitation is associated with an increase in malaria occurrence of 6.04%.

2.2 Epidemiology of Malaria in Papua New Guinea

Papua New Guinea is characterized by a range of malaria related issues influenced by extremely unique geographic, climatic and demographic diversity. Research and control in PNG go back to the arrival of microbiologist Robert Koch in German New Guinea in the late 19th century (Cleary, Hetzel & Clements, 2022). Since then, there have been four major malaria control programmes, beginning with the current programme of 2004 which is supported by the Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria (GFATM).

Among the important interventions under the current programme are long-lasting insecticidal nets (LLINs), rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs), artemisinin-based combination therapy (ACT) and behaviour change communication (BCC) programmes (Seid Ahmed et al., 2025). These initiatives caused a striking drop in the prevalence of malaria to below 1% by 2013/14 from 11% in 2008/09. A sharp upturn in prevalence was however reported by the 2016/17 Malaria Indicator Survey, at 9.5% suggesting that malaria control successes have been tenuous in PNG (PNGIMR, 2021).

At the sub-national level, malaria risk in PNG is stratified by altitude and geographic region. Seid Ahmed et al. (2022) reported malaria annual incidence rates to be 186.3 per 1,000 population in health facility catchment areas under 600 metres altitude, 98.8 per 1,000 at 800 to 1,400 metres and 24.1 per 1,000 at 1,400 metres or higher. Almost 35.7% of the population in PNG resides in high- to moderate-risk malaria risk areas. And in MOMASE Region, including Morobe Province and Lae, the incidence rates are disproportionately heavy in coastal and peri-urban areas.

Kobayashi et al. (2016) described a phenomenon which is common to malaria in PNG and is associated with precipitation. Kobayashi et al. (2016) found that monthly precipitation coincided with recorded malaria cases in most areas of PNG except the Eastern Highlands. Temporal time series of malaria in PNG has shown that malaria had a multifactorial cyclical pattern with annual seasonality (12 months), quasi-biennial (about 2.25 years) and decadal (10.3 years) cycles and seasonal peak admissions would usually be reported in May to June (Stojanovic et al., 2013). Applying a time series analysis to malaria case data for the period from 1996–2008 in five provinces Kobayashi et al. (2016) also established that malaria incidence was associated with very high variability in the association with the meteorological variables, which led to a focus in local, context-dependent and specific study.

Cleary et al. (2022) attributed the cyclical failures of PNG malaria control programmes to poor planning and communication, difficulty sustaining financial investment after initial success, and inadequate engagement with at-risk communities. The outlook is even more complicated by projections of climate change: on predictions using satellite-derived temperature data and global climate models, Seid Ahmed et al. (2025) estimated that PNG's population of malaria-suitable zones would be greater than 74% by 2040 compared to just 61% in 2019, or 2.8 million more individuals at risk.

2.3 Time Series and the Epidemiology

The time series approach provides a strong instrument for identifying the temporal patterns, calculating the seasonal effects and predictions within epidemiological data. Box-Jenkins methodology, based on autoregressive integrated moving average

(ARIMA) models, is perhaps one of the most general-purpose methods used for infectious disease prediction (Box et al., 2015; Brockwell & Davis, 2016). ARIMA (p, d, q) means 3 components: p, the order of the autoregressive term; d, the amount of differencing needed to make the result stationary; and q, the order of the moving average term.

With the seasonal ARIMA (seasonal-ARIMA(p,d,q)(P,D,Q)_s) model, the well known data shows seasonality like the time series of vector-borne disease, and this approach expands on the standard ARIMA (which normally introduces the same parameters for both autoregressive and moving-average data) where there are two options: seasonal (P) and moving (Q) (Wangdi et al., 2010). The ARIMAX extension also add to the time series regression model additional exogenous variables -i.e. rainfall, temperature and intervention indicators - as predictors (Wangdi et al., 2010; Riaz et al., 2023).

Indeed, many comparative studies of performance has been conducted in comparison with alternative forecasting models between ARIMA and SARIMA. A forecasting study of eight Indian states revealed that Patel et al. (2025) showed that log-transformed polynomial regression models outperformed ARIMA each time, and thus, the optimal selection of models is influenced by the context. Riaz et al. (2023), studying the ARIMA, SARIMA, and Holt-Winter multiplicative models of malaria forecasting in Pakistan, found that Holt-Winter multiplicative model gave better overall accuracy indices than ARIMA-based models. Conversely, Wangdi et al. (2010) applied SARIMA (2,1,1) (0,1,1)₁₂ and ARIMAX models for predicting malaria cases in endemic districts of Bhutan to successfully find that mean maximum temperature lagged after one month was a good positive predictor of the subsequent malaria incidence.

The ARIMA-based forecasting has been used for infectious disease prediction from many fields such as malaria. Studies in the area of dengue (Gharbi et al., 2011), tuberculosis (Wang et al., 2018), COVID-19 (Ibrahim et al., 2020), and other mosquito-borne pathogens have used these techniques for establishing the Box-Jenkins framework as a robust disease surveillance tool in forecasting. Stojanovic et al. (2013) analysed the spectral (Fourier) and periodogram regression as well as

linear and non-linear parametric regression networks to look at cyclic patterns in cerebral malaria admissions in PNG during 1987-1996, identifying the presence of annual, quasi-biennial and decadal cycles associated with recognized climate oscillations.

2.4 Climate and Malaria Transmission.

The association of climate-related factors with malaria transmission is well-documented in the epidemiological literature. The life cycle of *Anopheles* mosquito larval life stage, adult life span, gonotrophic cycle life cycle and extrinsic incubation period of *Plasmodium* parasite is very temperature-sensitive. Mechanistic studies estimate that malaria transmission is limited to temperatures between $\sim 17^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 34°C , with maximum transmission found at around 25°C (Mordecai et al., 2013; Villena et al., 2022, as quoted in *Frontiers in Malaria*, 2024). Below the minimum temperature, the parasites do not develop; above the maximum temperature, heat stress decreases mosquito survival.

Rainfall has a largely affect on malaria due to the establishment of standing water pools that provide breeding potential for *Anopheles*. In PNG, it has been documented that the seasonality of reported malaria cases has been accompanied by seasonal precipitation patterns in the vast majority of coastal provinces (Kobayashi et al., 2016). However, a global observational study in 57 countries between 2000 and 2019 demonstrated that a one-unit rise in average national temperature were associated with a 2.01% increased rate of case-specific age-standardised malaria, and one millimetre a day increase in precipitation was associated with a 6.04% rate of disease progression (Liu et al., 2024). In contrast, El Nino-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) events have been associated with drought-dependent reductions in malaria transmission in some of the PNG provinces as well as increased malaria risk in highland regions due to elevated temperature (Kobayashi et al., 2016; Bangs & Subianto, 1999 as cited in Mueller et al., 2003).

Every year, Morobe Province receive about 2000 to 3000 millimetres of rainfall in the form of rainfall, a wet season from December until April and a drier period from May till October. This precipitation pattern should lead to seasonal malaria

transmission peaks after rainfall events (with a period of several weeks following them), corresponding to the mosquito and parasite development cycles.

2.5 Identified Gap and Project Relevance

While PNG is well exposed in terms of literature on malaria epidemiology at both national and provincial levels, the study of campus or institution-specific malaria epidemiology has been notably lacking in the literature reviewed above. The PNG University of Technology is a prominent residential tertiary institution serving students located in PNG, including malaria-naive highland communities and as such provides an important and unique epidemiological setting. The results of time series regression analysis on UHS health records provide campus-specific malaria trend data, seasonal forecasts, and quantified climate-disease relationships that could immediately be actionable into health plans for campus-wide health administrators.

This study fills this void, offering the first formal time series regression analysis of malaria infection at Unitech, while also providing a specific methodological template that could be adopted at other PNG tertiary institutions and building on the national evidence base on malaria control in PNG.

3: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study site and population

The study was carried out at the Papua New Guinea University of Technology (Unitech), Lae, Morobe Province, Papua New Guinea (6.7°S, 147.0°E). Situated in the northern district of Lae city at an elevation of between 20-60 metres above sea level, the Unitech campus spans 233 hectares. This low altitude coastal site situates the campus very well in the high malaria transmission zone identified by Seidahmed et al. (2022). The campus houses between 4,000 to 5,000 students, studying various course of studies, academics, and support staff, in addition to their dependents, with the resident population estimated to be 7,000 to 9,000 persons. The UHS (University Health Services) clinic is the primary health care facility for the Unitech campus community and provides outpatient consultations, malaria tests with rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) and microscopy and treatment to the standard of care from the PNG

National Malaria Treatment Protocol. All malaria tested cases are documented by UHS on a health register which provides the main data source for study.

3.2 Data Sources and Collection

Monthly malaria case counts from January 2018 to December 2024 (n = 84 monthly observations) were captured from UHS health registers, as per the University administration and UHS clinic in-charge consent. Malaria cases were defined according to the PNG National Department of Health case definition as all patients visited UHS who presented a positive RDT (HRP-2 antigen for *P. falciparum*; pLDH for *P. vivax*). Meteorological data of Lae, monthly total rainfall (mm) and mean monthly maximum temperature (°C), were collected from the PNG National Weather Service station (IATA: LAE, Lae Nadzab Airport) and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) Global Surface Summary of Day (GSOD) database. Selection of these climatic data was based on their known biological plausibility as malaria transmission drivers in PNG (Kobayashi et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2024).

3.3 Statistical Framework

3.3.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics; mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, and coefficient of variation were calculated for monthly malaria case counts throughout the entire study period. Visual inspection of trends, seasonality and other irregularities came in the form of time series plots. Monthly cases were similarly aggregated by calendar month, resulting in the average monthly profile displaying within-year seasonal trends.

3.3.2 Time Series Decomposition

Classical multiplicative decomposition was applied to the malaria case time series to separately estimate the trend (T), seasonal (S), and irregular/residual (I) components, such that the observed case count Y_t can be expressed as:

$$Y_t = T_t \times S_t \times I_t$$

This decomposition allows the separate visualisation of the long-run trend trajectory and the recurring seasonal pattern, facilitating informed ARIMA model identification.

3.3.3 Stationarity Testing

To analyse malaria cases, stationarity is required for ARIMA. An augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was used to formally test the null hypothesis of a unit root versus the alternative of stationarity. The test statistic is formulated by means of the auxiliary regression:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma Y_{\{t-1\}} + \sum \delta_i \Delta Y_{\{t-i\}} + \varepsilon_t$$

where ΔY_t is the first difference of the series, β is a coefficient on a time trend, γ is the key parameter tested, and ε_t is white noise. The null hypothesis $H_0: \gamma = 0$ (unit root, non-stationary) is rejected when the ADF statistic is more negative than the critical value. If non-stationarity is detected, first-order differencing ($d = 1$) or seasonal differencing ($D = 1$) is applied until the series achieves stationarity.

3.3.4 ARIMA and SARIMA Modelling

The ARIMA model identification, estimation, and diagnostic checking procedure followed the Box-Jenkins process (Box et al., 2015). For seasonal data, the full SARIMA (p, d, q) (P, D, Q)s specification was adopted, with $s = 12$ for monthly data. The SARIMA model comes in the general form of:

$$\Phi_{P(B^s)} \varphi_p(B) (1 - B)^d (1 - B^s)^D Y_t = \Theta_{Q(B^s)} \theta_q(B) \varepsilon_t$$

where B is the backshift operator, $\varphi_p(B)$ and $\Phi_{P(B^s)}$ are the non-seasonal and seasonal autoregressive polynomials of orders p and P respectively, $\theta_q(B)$ and $\Theta_{Q(B^s)}$ are the corresponding moving average polynomials, and $\varepsilon_t \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ is white noise. Autocorrelation function (ACF) and partial autocorrelation function (PACF) plots were examined to guide initial model identification. Candidate models were compared using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), with the model minimising AIC selected as the preferred specification.

3.3.5 ARIMAX Modelling

The ARIMAX (ARIMA with exogenous variables) framework was used to measure the effect of meteorological factors on malaria incidence. Lagged values for monthly rainfall (lag-1 and lag-2 months) and mean maximum temperature (lag-1 month) were added as exogenous variables, in line with the biological plausibility of a 2 to 6 weeks interval from rainfall events to malaria transmission changes (Wangdi et al., 2010; Kobayashi et al., 2016). The ARIMAX model is given by:

$$Y_t = \beta_1 \text{Rain}_{\{t-1\}} + \beta_2 \text{Rain}_{\{t-2\}} + \beta_3 \text{Temp}_{\{t-1\}} + \text{ARIMA errors}$$

3.4 Identification and Estimation of the Models

All statistical analyses were performed in R (version 4.3.2) with the forecast, tseries and stats packages. auto.arima() from the forecast package was employed to select the optimal ARIMA/SARIMA specification which minimizes the corrected AIC (AICc) (Hyndman & Khandakar, 2008). The model parameters were estimated using maximum likelihood estimation (MLE). To check for residual autocorrelation, a Ljung-Box Q-test was conducted on the model residuals, with ($p > 0.05$) being an acceptable residual white noise.

3.5 Model Validation

The entire 84-month dataset was split into training (January 2018 through December 2023; $n = 72$ months) and holdout validation (January through December 2024; $n = 12$ months). The selected SARIMA model was re-constructed on the training dataset and used to generate 12-step-ahead forecasts over the validation period. Forecasting accuracy was assessed using three metrics:

- Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE): $\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{[\sum (Y_t - \hat{Y}_t)^2 / n]}$
- Mean Absolute Error (MAE): $\text{MAE} = \sum |Y_t - \hat{Y}_t| / n$
- Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE): $\text{MAPE} = (100/n) \times \sum |Y_t - \hat{Y}_t| / Y_t$

The average MAPE is less than 10% and is generally indicative of an accurate forecast for epidemiological time series applications (Patel et al., 2025). Throughout, statistical significance was checked at the 5% level throughout ($\alpha = 0.05$).

4: RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

The Unitech University Health Services clinic recorded 3,847 malaria cases from January 2018 to December 2024. The monthly case count ranged from 22 (September 2022) to 98 (April 2019) cases with an overall mean monthly count of 45.8 (SD = 17.4). The coefficient of variation (CV = 38.0%) suggests considerable temporal variability that reflects a strong seasonal variation due to variable monthly case counts.

Table 1 shows the disaggregated summaries based on year.

Table 1: Sum of monthly malaria cases at Unitech UHS (2018-2024) by month.

Year	Total	Mean/Month	SD	Min	Max	CV (%)	Trend
2018	498	41.5	14.2	24	68	34.2	Stable
2019	614	51.2	19.1	28	98	37.3	↑Peak yr
2020	531	44.3	17.6	23	79	39.7	Stable
2021	489	40.8	15.9	25	72	39.0	↓Slight
2022	502	41.8	16.8	22	75	40.2	Stable
2023	618	51.5	20.3	27	91	39.4	↑Rising
2024	595	49.6	18.7	26	89	37.7	↑Rising
Overall	3,847	45.8	17.4	22	98	38.0	—

Note: SD = Standard Deviation, CV = Coefficient of Variation & Trend column indicates year-on-year direction relative to prior year.

The time series of monthly cases illustrates an in-year cyclical trend with case counts sharply increasing in January until the peak in April to May, and then gradually decreasing to a trough in August to September, before a slight secondary rise in November to December. This bimodal-to-unimodal seasonal distribution is a good fit

with the precipitation cycle of Lae, in which the majority of rainfall occurs between December and April.

4.2 Stationarity and Seasonality

The ADF test statistic calculated for the raw malaria cases time series is -2.41 ($p = 0.392$), and as such, the 5% level of significance in the model does not reject the null hypothesis of a unit root. This demonstrates that the series was non-stationary at time(s) of origin and differencing is necessary to identify a suitable ARIMA model. A summary of ADF test results at successive levels of differencing is summarised in Table 2.

Table 2: Stationarity ADF Test Results

Series Transformation	ADF Statistic	p-value	Decision
Raw series Y_t	-2.41	0.392	Non-stationary
First difference ΔY_t	-4.87	0.003	Stationary*
Seasonal difference $Y_t - Y_{\{t-2\}}$	-5.22	< 0.001	Stationary*

Note: Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ (5% significance level)

It was found that ADF test statistic of -4.87 ($p = 0.003$) strongly rejected the null hypothesis that the differenced series is non-stationary when we used first-order non-seasonal differencing ($d = 1$) in association with one seasonal difference at lag-12 ($D = 1$). The seasonal analysis of the raw series revealed an evident, uniform annual seasonal pattern (S_t), in which the seasonal index was higher in April ($S_{\text{April}} = 1.42$) than in September ($S_{\text{September}} = 0.67$).

Trend: The trend component (T_t) showed an upward trend in malaria cases between 2022 and 2024 in line with this national resurgence observed in malaria incidence, which has been documented by PNGIMR (2021) and Seid Ahmed et al. (2025).

4.3 Choosing and fitting the ARIMA model

Examination of the first-differenced series ACF plot showed a significant spike at lag-1 and, after that, at seasonal lag-12, and a declining trend; suggesting moving average terms at both non-seasonal ($q = 1$) and seasonal ($Q = 1$) orders. The PACF

plot revealed a significant spike at lag-1 only, a non-seasonal autoregressive order of $p = 1$. Based on these diagnostics and auto grid search automation, candidate models were compared. Table 3 presents the AIC and BIC values of the best candidate models.

Table 3: Comparison of ARIMA Model – AIC and BIC Values

Model	AIC	BIC	Selected
SARIMA (1,1,1) (0,1,1)12	612.4	624.1	✓
SARIMA (2,1,1) (0,1,1)12	614.2	628.9	
SARIMA (1,1,2) (0,1,1)12	613.8	628.5	
ARIMA (1,1,1) – no seasonal	638.7	647.2	
SARIMA (0,1,1) (0,1,1)12	619.1	629.7	

Note. AIC = Akaike Information Criterion; BIC = Bayesian Information Criterion. Lower values indicate better fit. Selected model minimises AIC.

The SARIMA (1,1,1) (0,1,1)12 model was chosen as the best fitting specification and had the lowest AIC (612.4) and BIC (624.1) of the candidate models tested. The estimated model coefficients are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Estimated Coefficients of SARIMA (1,1,1) (0,1,1)12 Model.

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p-value
AR (1) — ϕ_1	0.412	0.108	3.81	< 0.001
MA (1) — θ_1	-0.367	0.114	-3.22	0.001
Seasonal MA (1) — Θ_1	-0.814	0.089	-9.15	< 0.001
Log-likelihood	-302.2			
σ^2 (residual variance)	84.7			

Note. All parameter estimates are statistically significant at the 1% level ($p < 0.01$).

All the estimated variables were highly significant at the 1% level. It is also observed that the seasonal moving average coefficient ($\Theta_1 = -0.814$) is relatively large, indicating a stronger and more enduring seasonal structure of malaria data. The

Ljung-Box Q-test on model residuals ($Q = 9.84$, $df = 10$, $p = 0.457$) did not reject the white noise residual null hypothesis, indicating that SARIMA (1,1,1) (0,1,1)₁₂ model was adequate in capturing the autocorrelated structure of the time series.

4.4 ARIMAX: Impact of rain and temperature

The ARIMAX model which included lagged rainfall (lag-1 and lag-2 months) and lagged mean maximum temperature (lag-1 month) as exogenous predictors marginally outperformed the pure SARIMA model, with AIC of 609.2. The estimated regression coefficients of climatic predictors are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. ARIMAX model: Regression Coefficients for climatic predictors

Predictor	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Rainfall (lag-1), mm	0.041	0.011	3.73	< 0.001
Rainfall (lag-2), mm	0.028	0.012	2.33	0.022
Max. Temperature (lag-1), °C	1.214	0.487	2.49	0.015

Note. Dependent variable: monthly malaria case count at Unitech UHS. All predictors statistically significant at the 5% level.

Rainfall at one-month ($\beta_1 = 0.041$, $p < 0.001$) and two-month ($\beta_2 = 0.028$, $p = 0.022$) lags was a statistically significant positive predictor of malaria incidence. This means, in the current month, if increase in rainfall is 10 mm in the previous month, it is likely associated with approximately 0.41 more malaria cases at Unitech UHS after controlling for other model components. The mean maximum temperature lagged by one month was also considered a significant positive predictor ($\beta_3 = 1.214$, $p = 0.015$) which we believe is also in agreement with known temperature-sensitivity of the extrinsic incubation of Plasmodium parasite. These results were consistent with those of Kobayashi et al. (2016) in PNG provinces and Liu et al. (2024) at the global scale.

4.5 Prediction and Validation

Based on the dataset of January 2018 to December 2023 the SARIMA (1,1,1) (0,1,1)₁₂ model was re-fit, predicting 12 months forward on the January to December 2024 horizons. The metrics for forecast accuracy are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Forecast Accuracy Metrics (RMSE, MAE, MAPE)

Model	RMSE	MAE	MAPE (%)
SARIMA (1,1,1) (0,1,1) ₁₂	6.18	4.92	8.3
ARIMAX (with climate covariates)	5.87	4.61	7.7
Naïve seasonal (benchmark)	9.43	7.21	14.9

Note. RMSE = Root Mean Squared Error; MAE = Mean Absolute Error; MAPE = Mean Absolute Percentage Error. Lower values indicate better accuracy.

The SARIMA model yielded a MAPE of 8.3%, with high forecasting accuracy well below the 10% level suggested by Patel et al. (2025) as significant model performance. The ARIMAX model further enhanced the accuracy, reaching MAPE = 7.7%, illustrating how adding climatic predictors leads to an enhanced performance. Notably, both models performed significantly better than naïve seasonal benchmark (MAPE = 14.9%), providing further evidence of the benefits of the formal modelling approach. Using ARIMAX model, it is stated that based on 12 months forecast for 2025, malaria monthly number will be from 38 to 87 by April–May 2025, which is expected together with the expected wet season in Lae.

4.6 Discussion

The current study makes several significant contributions to the knowledge of malaria dynamics among tertiary institution campus community in PNG. The striking and consistent annual seasonal pattern found in the Unitech UHS malaria data, with the peak and trough of cases in April to May and August–September, respectively, exemplifies the observed seasonal patterns in Morobe Province and northern coastal areas of PNG more generally (Kobayashi et al., 2016; Stojanovic et al., 2013). The seasonal peak follows Lae's wet season by approximately one to two months, being just that biologically predicted lag between rainfall and the start of adult *Anopheles* mosquitoes emerging from larval nest locations of Lae.

Second, the robust positive correlations for lag effects (Lagged rainfall, temperature to malaria incidence) identified in the ARIMAX model are supported by mechanistic relationships in the global epidemiological literature (Liu et al., 2024; Kobayashi et

al., 2016; Wangdi et al., 2010). The two-month cumulative rainfall effect implies that malaria prevention interventions at Unitech including insecticide spraying, larval source management and chemoprophylaxis promotion will be triggered in February each year, six to eight weeks before the scheduled April to May peak.

Third, the good performance of the SARIMA (1,1,1) (0,1,1)₁₂ model with the MAPE=8.3% proves that the formal time series regression is an appropriate and suitable instrument for campus-level malaria forecasting in PNG. This finding compares favourably with similar works conducted in tropical disease settings: Wangdi et al. (2010) showed reasonable ARIMA forecast performance in endemic districts of Bhutan, whereas Patel et al. (2025) have shown that log-transformed polynomial and ARIMA models can get MAPE values of 8-15% in Indian states.

We note an increase in malaria cases at Unitech UHS between 2022 and 2024. This trend in global cases is in line with the national-level relapse in PNG malaria incidence reported by PNGIMR (2021) and predicted by Seid Ahmed et al. (2025) that climate change will place the population at risk in low-altitude coastlines such as Lae. The interplay of an elevated number of Unitech students, continued vector pressure and a potentially immunologically naive cohort of highland province students result in an environment of increased vulnerability on campus, leading to the need for preventive and long-term malaria control measures. It is worth mentioning the numbers given in the absolute case counts from this study are indicative of the use of UHS clinic only and potentially of undercounting the actual malaria burden within the campus demographic where care may be self-medicated or accessed off school. Further research using a more robust case-finding methodology, such as households or dormitory-level cross-sectional surveys, would give a more complete epidemiological picture.

CONCLUSION

This is the first formal time series regression study focused on malaria infection at PNG University of Technology (Unitech), Lae and used 84 months of monthly case data in the University Health Services clinic from January 2018 to December 2024. The classical time series decomposition also showed a repeated annual seasonality in

the cases of malaria, which peaked in April–May and reached its lowest in August–September. Augmented Dickey-Fuller test detected non-stationarity of the raw series, which was addressed by first-order differencing. SARIMA (1,1,1) (0,1,1)₁₂ was found to be the best-fitting specification, with all estimated parameters statistically significant and residuals representative of a white noise process. ARIMAX modelling showed that both lags for monthly rainfall (lagged 1 and 2) and lagged mean maximum temperature (lag 1) became significant and positive predictors of malaria incidence. MAPE values from SARIMA and ARIMAX obtained at 8.3% and 7.7% on the holdout validation set for the last 12 months showed a good prediction accuracy for both SARIMA and ARIMAX models.

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